

Adsorptive cathodic stripping voltammetric determination of copper in fish samples

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A rapid differential pulse adsorptive stripping voltammetric method has been developed for the trace determination of copper in fish samples using picolinic acid. The base electrolyte used was 0.01 M NH₄Cl (pH 6.0). A well defined peak is observed at -0.26 V. Parameters like concentration of ligand, accumulation potential, accumulation time, rest period, drop size, scan rate, pulse amplitude etc. have been optimized. Under optimum conditions, the 3 σ detection limit was found to be 0.2 ppb. The method is highly selective and sensitive. The method has been applied to the determination of Cu^{II} in fish samples.

Copper is one of the most abundant trace metals in the environment. It is an essential micronutrient in almost all organisms. It occurs in varying concentrations in water, sediments and biota depending upon the activities in the surrounding area. One potentially important exposure route to human consumption is contaminated fish. Fishes are the major group of victims of industrial pollution since they come in direct contact with polluted water right from the birth. Bioaccumulation factor of 200 has been reported for copper¹. Consumption of contaminated fish may lead to copper poisoning. Chronic effects of copper in fish versus endocrine toxicity have been studied². Application of voltammetric techniques in the determination of copper and their disadvantages have been reviewed³. Adsorptive cathodic stripping voltammetry includes complexation of the metal with suitable ligand, adsorptive accumulation of the complex on electrode surface followed by cathodic scanning of potential to reduce the adsorbed species. Methods using oxine, pyrogallol red, dithizone, 1,10-phenanthroline, nioxime, catechol, α -benzyl monooxime have been reported for estimation of copper⁴.

This paper suggests a new adsorptive stripping voltammetric method for trace determination of copper using picolinic acid as a ligand. The method has been extended to the determination of copper in fish samples.

Results and discussion

The voltammograms of copper were recorded at vari-

ous concentrations of NH₄Cl from 0.001 M to 0.1 M. Concentration of 0.01 M was found to be most suitable in order to get well-defined peak. At lower concentration of NH₄Cl, the peak current-concentration relation was found to be non-linear while at higher concentration of NH₄Cl, the reproducibility was poor.

The pH of the solution was varied from 4.0 to 10.0 and it was observed that the peak height was maximum between pH 6.0 and 8.0 indicating higher conditional stability of the Cu^{II}-picolinic acid complex under this condition. The peak was found to be symmetric and well defined at pH 6.0 and hence this pH was selected. The peak potential was found to be -0.26 V. Concentration of picolinic acid was varied from 5 μ M to 200 μ M. The peak current was found to increase with the concentration up to 100 μ M. After that, it remained almost constant. Ligand concentration of 100 μ M was selected for further studies. In the absence of ligand, no peak was observed at these concentrations of copper. The accumulation period was varied from 5 to 120 s while the solution was stirred. It was observed that the peak current increases with accumulation period up to 30 s and decrease slowly with further increase in accumulation period. Accumulation period of 30 s was selected followed by rest period of 15 s.

With increase in surface area of the mercury drop, a linear increase in peak current was observed and a drop size of 1.4 mm² was maintained for all the studies. Increase in the scan rate and pulse amplitude showed an

increase in the peak current. Scan rate of 20 mV/s and pulse amplitude of 30 mV were selected. At higher pulse amplitude, the signals are not reproducible.

Interference of other metal ions like Co^{II} , Mn^{II} , Pb^{II} , Cr^{III} , Cr^{V} , Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} , Ni^{II} , Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} was studied. It was observed that increasing the concentration of these ions except Cr^{VI} individually or together from 1 to 100 times excess did not affect the symmetry or peak height. The peak height of copper reduces slowly with increase in the concentration of Cr^{VI} . When Cr^{VI} is present in 100 times higher concentration, the peak height reduces by about 40 percent.

Hence the following conditions were selected for the further studies : concentration of NH_4Cl = 0.01 M; pH = 6.0, concentration of picolinic acid = 100 μM , accumulation potential = -0.0 V, accumulation period = 30 s, rest period = 15 s, drop size = 1.4 mm^2 , scan rate = 20 mV/s, pulse amplitude = 30 mV.

The 3σ detection limit was found to be 0.2 ppb. Equation of regression line is $Y = 1.945 X + 0.4$ with coefficient of correlation 0.9990. The voltammograms show neither copper nor picolinic acid alone give peak in the potential range under study, but a distinct peak is observed when both are present in the solution (Fig. 1), indicating formation of complex.

Fig. 1. Voltammograms of (A) 0.001 M NH_4Cl with 100 μM picolinic acid, (B) 0.001 M NH_4Cl with 10 ppb Cu^{II} and (C) 0.01 M NH_4Cl with 100 μM picolinic acid and 5, 10 and 15 ppb Cu^{II} .

Application of the method :

The method was applied to the determination of copper in fish samples. Fish samples were collected from local markets in Nagpur and Mumbai, two cities in India.

The fish were cleaned with double distilled water. Muscles were taken out and dried in sunlight. These were crushed to a fine powder form. 0.5 g of the sample was weighed, 10 ml conc. HNO_3 and 0.4 g magnesium nitrate and a few porcelain pieces were added and digested on hot plate for 5 h. The beaker was placed in muffle furnace at 500°C for 30 min. After cooling, 10 ml of 6 M HCl was added and heated on water bath until the white residue dissolved. Volume was made up to 50 ml. Suitable aliquots were taken and the voltammograms were recorded. The results obtained by present method and checked by AAS method are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Analysis of copper in fish samples

Sl. no.	Name of fish	Place	Concentration of copper ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	
			Present method	AAS method
1.	Shilat	Mumbai	2.67 \pm 0.10	2.73
2.	Jalva	Mumbai	13.83 \pm 0.20	13.73
3.	Sukat	Mumbai	15.06 \pm 0.35	15.28
4.	Prawn	Nagpur	7.53 \pm 0.13	7.45
5.	Marrel	Nagpur	6.13 \pm 0.06	5.95
6.	Vogte	Nagpur	5.48 \pm 0.21	5.50
7.	Crabs	Nagpur	4.41 \pm 0.12	4.45

^a(Avg \pm SD) of 4 observations.

Conclusion :

A simple rapid method has been developed for the determination of Cu^{II} at trace level. The method was found to be reproducible, reliable and accurate. Selectivity and sensitivity are reasonably high. An important advantage of the method over previously known methods is that 30 s of accumulation period is sufficient to achieve the sensitivity of 0.2 ppb. The sample treatment is rapid and simple. This method is more sensitive than many of the previously known methods⁴. Standard deviation, relative mean deviation and coefficient of variation at 1 ppb were found to be 0.07, 3.1 and 4.0% respectively. The results obtained for fish samples are found to be in good agreement with those given by AAS method.

Experimental

Apparatus : Differential Pulse Adsorptive Cathodic Stripping Voltammetric (DPAdCSV) studies were carried out using Metrohm Polarecord E-506 serie-03 working on 220 volts stabilized AC mains. To it was connected the Metrohm polarography stand E-505. The instrument was kept in an air-conditioned room maintained at 25 \pm 1°C and humidity between 50 to 60.

The electrode assembly consisted of the hanging mercury drop electrode (Kemula type) as the working electrode, Ag/AgCl (sat. KCl) electrode as reference electrode and a platinum electrode as an auxiliary electrode. Nitrogen gas was used for deaeration and micropipette (25 μ l) was used for addition of Cu^{II} solution. Mercury was purified by aeration method and then distilled under reduced pressure in a mercury distillation unit.

Reagents and solutions : All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The solutions were prepared in double distilled water. A stock solution of 100 ppb Cu^{II} was prepared and desired dilutions were made as per the requirements. A 0.1 M solution of picolinic acid was prepared in 100 ml double distilled water.

General procedure : In each determination, 0.01 M NH₄Cl was maintained in total volume of 25 ml. The pH was adjusted to 6.0 using dil. NH₃ and dil. HCl solution. To it 25 μ l of picolinic acid solution was added using micropipette, which made the concentration of ligand 100 μ M. Copper solution of desired concentration was added using micropipette. The solution was deaerated with nitrogen for 10 min before actual recording. In all cases,

blank recordings were performed and necessary corrections were made in the calculations.

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